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O'ZBEK ETNOMADANIYATINING ESTETIK XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. Etnomadaniyat xalqning tarixiy-madaniy paradigmasidan chuqur joy olgan, uning yadrosiga aylangan, hayotiy, badiiy-estetik, falsafiy-gnoseologik, transsendental izlanishlari jarayonida shakllangan moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklarning yig'indisidir. Unda nafaqat o'tmish tajribalari, kelajak haqidagi tasavvurlar, sotsium duch kelayotgan vazifalarni hal etishga yo'naltirilganlik, balki inson qalbini, ruhini go'zal tuyg'ular, estetik g'oyalar bilan boyitish maqsadi ham mujassamdir. Etnomadaniyat shunchaki moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar yig'indisi emas, unda aniq etnoestetik qadriyatlar ham mavjud. Ushbu etnoestetik qadriyatlarni e'tibordan chetda qoldirish etnomadaniyatning nafaqat estetik, shuningdek ijtimoiy-tarbiyaviy, psixologik va ma'naviy ta'sirini ham susaytiradi. Etnoestetika etnomadaniyatdagi go'zallik va xunuklik, ulug'vorlik va tubanlik, fojiaiylik va kulgililik kabi estetik qadriyatlarni ifoda etuvchi fenomendir. Shu bois yshbu maqolada etnoestetikaning mohiyati ochib berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: etnomadaniyat, etnoestetika, etnos, xalq ijodi, san'at, o'zbek, qadriyat, doston, badiiy-estetik, sub'ekt.

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ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ЭТНОКУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация. Этнокультура глубоко укоренена в историко-культурной парадигме народа, формируя её ядро и проявляясь в процессах жизненных, художественно-эстетических, философско-гносеологических и трансцендентальных поисков. Она представляет собой совокупность материальных и духовных ценностей. Этнокультура воплощает не только

прошлый опыт и представления о будущем, но и стремится решать общественные задачи, обогащая человеческие сердца и души прекрасными чувствами и эстетическими идеалами. Этнокультура – это не просто собрание материального и духовного богатства, но также включает в себя специфические этноэстетические ценности. Игнорирование этих этноэстетических ценностей снижает не только эстетическое, но и социально-воспитательное, психологическое и духовное воздействие этнокультуры. Этноэстетика – это феномен, выражающий эстетические ценности, такие как красота и безобразие, величие и низость, трагичность и комизм в этнокультуре. В связи с этим данной статье раскрываются этноэстетические аспекты этнокультуры

Ключевые слова: этнокультура, этноэстетика, этнос, народное творчество, искусство, узбекский, ценности, эпос, художественно-эстетический, субъект.

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AESTHETIC FEATURES OF UZBEK ETHNOCULTURE

Abstract. Ethnoculture is deeply rooted in the historical and cultural paradigm of a nation, forming its core and emerging through the processes of vital, artistic-aesthetic, philosophical-gnoseological, and transcendental explorations. It is an aggregate of material and spiritual values. Ethnoculture embodies not only past experiences and visions of the future but also aims to solve societal challenges and enrich human hearts and souls with beautiful feelings and aesthetic ideals. Ethnoculture is not merely a collection of material and spiritual wealth but also encompasses specific ethno-aesthetic values. Ignoring these ethno-aesthetic values diminishes not only the aesthetic but also the social-educational, psychological, and spiritual impact of ethnoculture. Ethno-aesthetics is a phenomenon that expresses aesthetic values such as beauty and ugliness, grandeur and baseness, tragedy and comedy within ethnoculture. In connection with this, in this article we seek to reveal the ethno-aesthetical aspects of ethnic culture.

Keywords: ethnoculture, ethno-aesthetics, ethnos, folk art, art, Uzbek, value, epic, artistic-aesthetic, subject.

Introduction

Folk art and artistic works reflect the active artistic-aesthetic relationships of the people with the world and their surroundings. As a creator and innovator, the people cannot remain passive in response to the events, occurrences, and changes happening in the social reality. Therefore, Uzbek folk art and artistic works express

the artistic-aesthetic reflection of the social, historical, spiritual, political, and economic events that have occurred in the life of the Uzbek people. These are not precise, factual depictions of events but rather their expression filtered through the artistic-aesthetic world, tastes, worldview, and values of the people. As such, these works embody elements of fantasy, intuition, irrationality, exaggeration, artistic fiction, hyperbole, and futuristic perspectives. Most importantly, the people have elevated their lives and heroes to the level of real depictions and objective phenomena, where the artistic-aesthetic methods serve the artistic idea.

In folk art and artistic works, aesthetic realities such as beauty, ugliness, grandeur, baseness, tragedy, and humor are depicted in accordance with ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic heritage. These works express the noble qualities of the Uzbek people, their visions of beautifying life, and their hopes and aspirations. At the same time, folk art and artistic works also portray the ugliness, baseness, tragedy, immorality, and inhuman vices encountered in human character, morality, and behavior. In these depictions, noble purposes and virtues triumph over these flaws, and folk heroes become societal ideals.

In the epics found in the ethnocultural heritage, the people's ideals are depicted in the style of grotesque realism. The noble and virtuous qualities in these epics fully align with ethnocultural traditions, while ethno-aesthetic representations imbue these qualities with a national-ethnic essence.

Materials and methods

Scholars from CIS countries have conducted research on various aspects of ethnoculture, including M.M. Bakhtin, D.S. Likhachev, Yu.V. Bromley, S.N. Ikonnikova, M.S. Kagan, M.A. Nekrasova, T.A. Klimenkova, L.N. Kogan, Yu.V. Lotman, S.P. Mamontov, Ya.V. Chesnov, L.N. Gumilyov, E.V. Sokolev, I.E. Shirshov, G.N. Volkov, G.D. Baybekova, I.B. Orlova, B.V. Markov, K.A. Sergeev, T.A. Akindinova, T.A. Apinyan, M.O. Shavaeva, and others. Among them, the research of N.Ya. Bichurin and L.N. Gumilyov on the role of ancient Turkic tribes in shaping the Eurasian civilization is particularly valuable.

In scientific research dedicated to studying the folk art, artistic, aesthetic, and axiological aspects of Uzbek culture, philosophers and aestheticians such as E. Umarov, U. Qoraboev, A. Sher, M. Nurmatova, B. Khusanov, and D. Qodirova hold a special place. Their works and studies philosophically highlight the significance of artistic-aesthetic values that have played a crucial role in the formation of Uzbek culture.

This article references the following works: M.V. Loginova's article "Ethno-aesthetics in the System of Ethnoculture: Theoretical and Methodological Aspect" (2021), U.H. Qoraboev's books "Madaniyat Masalalari" (Issues of Culture) (2009) and "Etnokultura (Traditsionnaya Narodnaya Kultura)" (Ethnoculture: Traditional Folk Culture) (2005), A. Sher and B. Khusanov's "Estetika" (Aesthetics) (2010), S. Bulatov's "Uzbek Folk Applied Decorative Art" (1991), U.A. Utanova's dissertation "The Development of Folk Culture in Independent Uzbekistan

(Philosophical and Cultural Approach)” (2008), and M.O. Shavaeva’s dissertation “Ethnoculture as a Multifunctional System of Interaction” (2004).

In the preparation of this article, methods such as analysis and synthesis, retrospective analysis, and comparative analysis were used.

Discussion and results

Today, positive changes are taking place in the spirituality of our people, in the education of our youth, in mastering science, and in the creation of intellectual property. However, the study, synthesis of these achievements, identification of existing problems, and finding rational solutions to address them—thereby developing scientifically grounded methods for strengthening ethnocultural ties—lag behind practical needs. Social reality, including ethnocultural life, does not develop on its own; it is influenced by external and internal factors. This necessitates studying ethnocultural life, its positive and negative manifestations, and developing scientific methods and recommendations that align with the demands of national development.

The relevance and necessity of this research can be justified as follows:

- Firstly, the education of a highly spiritual and well-rounded generation requires extensive use of ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic wealth created over centuries and tested through various historical periods.

- Secondly, since ethnoculture embodies the perceptions of beauty, elegance, grandeur, and artistic-aesthetic ideals of our people, it must be studied from a philosophical-aesthetic perspective.

- Thirdly, ethnoculture is the quintessence of historical-cultural and spiritual values, artifacts, and gnoseological explorations. However, it serves to strengthen diachronic connections only through its artistic-aesthetic images, means of expression, and methods of influencing people's consciousness and psyche. Without these functions, the essence of ethnoculture, as well as its role and significance in national spiritual development, cannot be understood.

- Fourthly, the aesthetic essence and functions of ethnoculture, especially the philosophical-methodological issues of ethno-aesthetic theory, have not sufficiently attracted researchers' attention. Meanwhile, almost all concepts about ethnoculture reference ethno-aesthetic theory. Thus, studying the philosophical-methodological issues of ethno-aesthetics is a pressing scientific need.

The relevance of this research is reflected in defining "ethno-aesthetics as a component of ethnic culture." Ethno-aesthetic values serve as a unique "cultural code" that embodies the identity of an ethnos. The affiliation of aesthetics with the field of culture is so evident that the formula "ethno-aesthetics as part of ethnoculture" requires no proof. However, this formula gains deeper meaning when the role of aesthetics in the modern conditions of the existence of ethnos is brought into question [Loginova M.V., 2021. p 169].

When aesthetics takes folk culture as its object of study, it relies on the methods, categories, and conclusions of the science of aesthetics. However, even if it develops into a separate scientific field or theory in the future, it cannot distance

itself from the socio-cultural space. Ethno-aesthetics draws on the experiences of a people in evaluating beauty and ugliness in a distinctive way, on their mentality regarding grandeur or baseness, and on ethnostereotypes related to tragedy and comedy. The cultural scholar U.H. Qoraboev, who studied the philosophical, social, and historical aspects of ethnoculture, writes:

"Folk culture, first of all, is the culture of the population of a certain territory (place); second, it is the culture of the working people, the masses; third, it is the culture of a specific ethnos... In a broad sense, all culture that expresses the ideological positions, aspirations, and inner world of the people, as well as the culture created by professionals, can be called folk culture" [Qoraboev U.H., 2005. p. 22–23].

From this definition, it can be understood that folk culture is the collection of material and spiritual values created by a specific ethnos and its representatives. When classifying these values, the researcher emphasizes traditional cultural forms and, based on all areas and activities of human life, states:

"Culture is not just one area of life. It is not limited to science, enlightenment, religion, literature, art, creativity, and positive traditions. Culture manifests itself in all aspects of human life and is essential for all areas" [Qoraboev U., 2009. p. 5].

U.A. Utanova, who has conducted specialized philosophical research on folk culture, evaluates it from the conceptual perspective:

- 1) as the substance of the formation of people, nation, and ethnos;
- 2) as the measure and product of human and societal development;
- 3) as the social environment ensuring the development and transformation of society;
- 4) as a phenomenon in which the traditionality and historicity of folk culture have formed a core that serves modernity, thereby turning the entire culture of the people into a stable, enduring reality.

As a result, she concludes that folk culture is "a collection of the material and spiritual values created by a particular ethnos or people over a long process of social and historical development, the social and gnoseological experience they have gained in their activities aimed at perceiving, understanding, and transforming the world, and the quintessence of their perceptions of the past, present, and future" [Utanova U.A., 2008. p. 15].

In our opinion, U.A. Utanova has accurately grasped the fundamental characteristics of ethnoculture.

Research shows that the issue of ethno-aesthetics has been insufficiently studied in science. This can be attributed to "the crisis of worldview currently experienced by the field of aesthetics. This crisis is influenced by the postmodernist 'mosaic' culture, which tends to marginalize ethnic values. However, the growing level of ethnic self-awareness necessitates the development of methodological approaches to human artistic practices and lifestyles" [Loginov M.V., 2013. p. 41–45].

Postmodernist "mosaic" culture is a cultural concept of the postmodern era, representing a cultural environment in the modern world characterized by diversity,

variability, and a "mosaic" composition. It emerged in the second half of the 20th century as a result of globalization, the development of information technologies, and changes in human consciousness. The term "mosaic culture" refers to a culture that is unstructured and composed of diverse elements. This culture lacks a single center or clear norms and reflects the coexistence and interaction of various sources, perspectives, traditions, and styles.

"Mosaic culture is a socio-cultural state characterized by the random and disordered perception of various types of information by many subjects. In this state, the information does not transform into hierarchically organized structures in the subject's consciousness but rather consists of 'fragmented pieces,' connected randomly by the proximity of the information acquisition time, resonance, or associations of ideas" [https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Мозаичная_культура].

The concept of mosaic culture was developed by the French social psychologist Abraham Moles. According to Moles, the emergence of mosaic culture is closely tied to the activities of mass media, which are often targeted at an audience with a relatively low intellectual level.

Postmodernist "mosaic" culture possesses characteristics such as diversity, pluralism, relativity of meanings, harmony between the new and the old, blending of cultural facets, creative freedom, a semblance of disorder and "chaos," personal identity, intercultural dialogue, aesthetic and creative development, and a global cultural space. Thus, postmodernist "mosaic" culture is a cultural reflection of changes in human thinking and social life, highlighting diversity, relativity, and cultural variability.

Moreover, the under-researched status of ethno-aesthetics in science is not due to a lack of artistic and aesthetic sources or unexplored research objects but rather to the impossibility of directly observing the experiences, emotions, and fantasies of the subject (the people) of folk art and culture. For this reason, there is a tradition of analyzing and studying the subject's life-aesthetic position and artistic ideas through the views expressed by the creator or their colleagues and associates. However, this approach cannot always be applied to objectively study and understand the processes of artistic-aesthetic perception of reality in folk art and culture.

In the social and humanitarian sciences, "interest in the aesthetic values of folk culture emerged in the 1970s. The development of ethno-aesthetics is a result of the modern state of culture, which can be explained by several objective reasons. First, the second half of the 20th century saw the crisis of postmodernism, which had been regarded as the dominant philosophy. A.V. Rykov, in one of his recent works, describes postmodernism as 'radical conservatism,' defining its main principle as 'rejection of representation,' which breaks the chain of 'art – subject – social reality.' Second, the globalization of culture and the integration of knowledge have led to an increased interest in the uniqueness of human and ethnic life. Finally, third, the necessity of studying the aesthetic perceptions of ethnos independently and comprehensively has arisen" [Loginov M.V., 2013. p. 41–45].

Every ethnos possesses a distinctive aesthetic worldview and cultural values. These constitute the cultural heritage of the ethnos, and their in-depth study plays a crucial role in understanding and preserving ethnic identity.

The criteria and methods of ethno-aesthetics are derived from the content of ethnoculture, its creative works, artifacts, and traditions, which have become its components. This approach allows us to study ethnoculture objectively and in its entirety, without external pressures or artificially created theoretical models. Of course, we utilize theoretical models and methodologies from disciplines such as aesthetics, art studies, folk art, the philosophy of art, and the history of art. However, these must align with the immanent laws of ethnoculture.

During the analysis of the subject of culture, various approaches and perspectives emerge in the scientific discourse. It must be emphasized that the question of the subject of culture lies at the core of ethnoculture. The axiom that culture is the product of human activity does not yet answer the question of who exactly constitutes the subject of culture: individual persons, certain groups or strata, or the people, the masses, the nation.

"Summarizing all elements of ethnoculture, ethnic processes, and their outcomes, it can be concluded that the ethnos itself is both the object, subject, and carrier of ethnoculture. In this regard, ethnoculture becomes a system of interpersonal and intercultural interactions (which also includes the interaction between ethnic and global cultures)" [Shavaeva M.O., 2004. p. 11].

From its etymological interpretation, ethnoculture comprises the wealth and artifacts (artificial realities and worlds created in the process of social activity) produced by the ethnos (the people). Nevertheless, it cannot ignore the question of the role played by individuals, groups, and strata who have created cultural treasures, made unique discoveries, and produced great works.

As the renowned art critic and philosopher M.S. Kagan put it, there is a need to move "from the intuitive perception of wholeness to the theoretical understanding of its highly complex and polyfunctional system" [Kagan M.S., 1998. p. 9]. Without such an approach, it will be impossible to halt the spread of contradictory, sometimes utterly incorrect, unrealistic, and unscientific views about the relationship between material and spiritual culture, civilization and culture, and the various forms, manifestations, and architectonics of cultural activity.

The subject of folk art refers to the individuals or groups who actively participate in folk creativity, preserving, adapting, and advancing the culture, traditions, and creative heritage of the people. These subjects are individuals who reflect the historical memory, national culture, and socio-psychological perspectives of the people. Typically, the subjects of folk art include artisans (such as those engaged in handicrafts, blacksmithing, pottery, hat-making, embroidery, jewelry-making, sewing, and other traditional crafts), oral performers (storytellers, epic narrators, folk singers, and those who recount fables, tales, and stories), artists (dancers, musicians, singers, and traditional performers), and preservers of cultural traditions (organizers of national festivals, customs, and rituals).

The role of the subject of folk art in society is threefold: first, they ensure that the historical and cultural values of the people are passed down from generation to generation; second, they unify communities (families and the nation) through cultural events; and third, they serve to impart national culture to the younger generation, fostering respect for it.

When the subject focuses on events or phenomena that interest or captivate them, they:

1. Do not always realize or consider that they cannot fully grasp or encompass these events.

2. Respond to these events emotionally, following their affective experiences.

3. Rely on their artistic-aesthetic experience and style.

Even creators of epic tales, who have the potential to depict events in their entirety, often choose one or a few comprehensible and relatable issues from reality to portray. They structure the system of images, the coherence of plots, and the composition of their work around these limited, simple, and understandable themes. For example:

- The composition of the epic “Alpomish” is built around the estrangement between brothers and the romantic adventures of the main characters.

- The epic “Bahrom and Gulandom” focuses on King Khisrav having a child in his old age and Bahrom's quest to find Gulandom.

- The epic “Farhad and Shirin” revolves around similar plotlines.

The linear progression of characters' actions, their direction, and even their movement within the artistic-aesthetic space are not as broad or complex as in works by recognized authors like Homer, Aeschylus, Shakespeare, or Joyce. Simplicity, clarity, and accessibility are hallmarks of folk art and culture.

Folk creativity – seen in epics, songs, proverbs, and legends – depicts the lives, daily routines, and aspirations of ordinary people. This simplicity makes it understandable and relatable to a wide audience. Folk creativity is expressed in straightforward and fluent language. This language is not restricted to the literate but is comprehensible to all, as it is created in the vernacular. The simplicity of folk creativity does not mean it lacks depth. On the contrary, folk art encapsulates profound truths of life through concise and clear expressions.

Additionally, the simplicity of folk art ensures that it is understood and appreciated by people of all ages and social groups. Even children can easily grasp folk songs, tales, and riddles. For this reason, folk art serves as a source of high literature and art, attracting people through its simplicity and clarity.

However, "accessibility" does not imply that anyone can perform folk epics or engage in crafts such as metalworking, wood carving, plasterwork, ceramics, composing, or tightrope walking without specialized skills. These forms of folk art require specific abilities and a sense of artistic-aesthetic taste. By accessibility, we mean that the types of creativity and art mentioned above are understandable to the general public and resonate with their artistic-aesthetic tastes and ideals.

An artist's artistic-aesthetic consciousness, thinking, and even genius cannot fully encompass reality. However, this does not negate the human ability to perceive,

create, and craft beautiful, unique, and ingenious works. Such masterpieces can be found in abundance in folk art and culture. Despite the limitations of human cognition, people strive to refine and elevate the uniqueness and beauty initiated by nature through their intellect, hands, and artistic-aesthetic abilities. To achieve this, they must remain inseparable from the surrounding reality and life, living in harmony with their needs.

In folk art and culture, this is reflected in how heroes live in alignment with the interests of their communities, how folk craftsmen continue creating essential patterns, carvings, and decorations, and how folk performers and artists present songs, melodies, and performances that resonate with the masses. It is essential to remember that folk art and culture, first and foremost, are artistic-aesthetic creations, encompassing intuition, fantasy, fabrication, irrationality, and subjectivism – elements that do not always correspond to objective reality.

Thus, it is not always appropriate to search for depictions in folk art and cultural works that fully align with reality or social life, or to trace their genesis to a specific historical period or social relationships. This is particularly true for works and plots that have taken shape over centuries, making such endeavors challenging.

Debates in aesthetics over rationality versus irrationality, realism versus utopia, and reality versus fantasy have yet to reach a universal conclusion. The inherent connection of artistic-aesthetic creation to individual characteristics, internal emotional experiences, and the dispersive distribution of ever-changing thoughts prevents these debates from being resolved. The pluralism of artistic-aesthetic ideas, experiences, and explorations – representing a form of democratic expression – continues to bring these discussions back to the fore.

When a subject draws inspiration for artistic-aesthetic needs and interests from nature, reality, and life, they must consider their realism. This necessitates a rational approach to reality. At the same time, rationality protects the subject from becoming entirely dependent on and bound to reality. An unwavering realist, who directs their entire consciousness, intellect, and focus exclusively on reality, sees nothing beyond it, and refuses to acknowledge anything else, is no different from a mere copyist or imitator.

Therefore, a true artist focuses their intellect and creative aspirations on understanding real life while avoiding complete dependence on it. The subject overcomes this dichotomy by distancing themselves from reality and recognizing their role as a subject and creator. Artists refer to this method as "viewing the mosaic from a distance." To fully grasp a mosaic a combination of fragments of stone and glass painted in different colors one must step back and view it from a certain distance.

In this way, rationality does not mean absolute attachment to reality; instead, it requires the subject to step back from it and view it from a distance to bring their artistic-aesthetic ideas to fruition. It is at this point of distancing that the subject engages in irrational, fantastical, and intuitive explorations.

In popular belief, the world is created in harmony. Actions or behaviors that go against this harmony, as well as immoral conduct, evoke disgust among the

people. Consequently, they have sung about and depicted ideal notions of good morals, universal harmony, and a society built on justice while condemning anything that opposes these ideals. Viewing reality and life through the lens of harmony has prevented irrational, fantastical, and intuitive pursuits from serving aesthetic separatism, instead keeping them within the boundaries of harmony. This, in essence, is a triumph of reason and rationality.

Intuition plays a critical role in artistic creation. Intuition is a form of cognition based on a person's experience, knowledge, and feelings, which does not require deep conscious reasoning. In the process of artistic creation, intuition often manifests as a source of inspiration. During moments of inspiration, the creator frequently relies on their emotions and inner world. In this process, intuition provides the creator with new ideas, images, and plots. Through intuitive sensations, the creator assigns new meanings to details of real life. At the same time, intuition helps the creator shape their images. For instance, a poet or artist might intuitively use specific colors or phrases in their work to convey a mood. Often, creators develop the main idea of their work without a precise plan, relying solely on their inner feelings. During this intuitive process, they unify their thoughts and emotions to create the overall meaning of the work.

Intuition is not only vital during the creative process but also in evaluating completed works. A creator can intuitively sense the strengths and weaknesses of their work and how it might affect others. Intuition often depends on the creator's personal experience. These inner feelings are rooted in the creator's advanced knowledge and expertise. Even inexperienced creators can possess intuition, but their intuitive understanding improves as they gain more experience. In artistic creation, intuition is crucial at every stage, not just for generating new ideas. It helps creators integrate their emotions, knowledge, and experiences to produce deeper and more impactful works.

From the above analysis, it is evident that folk art and culture are not solely based on rationality but also include various artistic-aesthetic approaches. Even in types of folk art and culture aimed at meeting practical needs, such as metalworking, plasterwork, or hat-making, we find fantastical and irrational elements. For example, the metalwork school of Bukhara astonishes with the fantastical forms and designs of its "surmadon" (antique containers for storing kohl). Similar elements can be observed in the metalworking arts of Khiva, Kokand, and Tashkent [Bulatov S., 1991. p. 274–276].

In Khiva's metalworking art, stylized representations of the sun, moon, and stars hint at a cosmic worldview. Additionally, depictions of real-life animals alongside fantastical creatures are common. In Kokand's metalworking, ornate patterns featuring fantastical flowers and vine-like motifs are widespread, expressing a love for nature. Patterns reflecting the sun and its rays are often depicted as central elements. Tashkent's metalworking school, renowned for its finesse and stylistic diversity, combines fantastical patterns with geometric shapes presented in abstract forms. Mythical figures, such as fairies and winged creatures, are also depicted.

In these fantastical designs, real-life images are harmonized with mythical, natural, and geometric shapes. Each pattern carries its own meaning and symbolism. For example, stars may represent virtue, while flowers symbolize life and eternity.

In the architecture of mosques and madrasas, especially in ceramics, minarets, and column decorations, irrational motifs and symbolic depictions encouraging transcendence are commonly found. The most important aspect is that these fantastical and irrational elements, along with symbolic depictions, serve the primary artistic-aesthetic purpose of the work, imparting it with grandeur, mystery, majesty, and sublimity.

Due to the constant significant interactions within ethnoculture, certain local or regional cultural markers may become particularly active and attempt to influence or draw other local and regional traditions into their orbit. Not all local or regional traditions within an ethnos display the same level of activity; typically, one or two take the lead. This process can be referred to as "internal integration within ethnoculture." Significant processes within ethnoculture allow for the widespread dissemination and development of certain types of folk art and culture in specific regions. As a result, local and regional traditions develop distinct characteristics, leading to ethno-aesthetic pluralism. This, in turn, encourages the subjects of folk art and culture to favor specific artistic-aesthetic styles.

For instance, in the Fergana Valley, craftsmanship such as decorative painting (naqsh), the traditional art of "askiya" (witty verbal contests), and tightrope walking are widespread. In the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, rituals like "kokpari" (a traditional equestrian game) and "bozabozlik" (a form of festive gathering) are prevalent. In Khorezm, traditions related to "surnay" (a wind instrument), "qayroqchilik" (metalworking), and fire-worship rituals have become widespread.

Not all works within ethnoculture can be described as created with exceptional skill and artistic-aesthetic taste. Among them, there are certainly works that are weak in terms of ideas and artistic-aesthetic quality. These do not stand out with unique ideas or artistic depictions, and their existence may be unknown to anyone but narrow specialists. However, those creations that portray reality and life's challenges with exceptional artistic-aesthetic mastery, reflect people's dreams and visions of a happy future, and fill hearts with noble aspirations hold a significant place in ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic heritage – even if they employ fantastical, irrational, or utopian styles.

This suggests that the people do not always prioritize artistic-aesthetic styles themselves but value works that, through these styles, serve to beautify and humanize life and existence, preserving them as part of their ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic legacy.

The main goal of ethnoculture and ethno-aesthetics is to form cultural or aesthetic ideals within individuals and society. Achieving an ideal in creativity and art is not an unattainable goal. There are unique, rare, and extraordinarily beautiful works in the fields of creativity and art that can be accepted as ideals. The Uzbek people have depicted as ideals heroes with bravery and noble qualities, as well as loyal, graceful, and beautiful women with fairy-like qualities. Occasionally,

inappropriate actions or missteps by these characters do not prevent them from being accepted as perfect figures.

At the same time, ideals undergo transformation; their traditional characteristics and behaviors are complemented by modern elements. An ideal that does not align with contemporary artistic-aesthetic tastes or the demands of the time fails to capture the interest of the audience. For this reason, certain types of folk art and culture are sometimes met with passive observation or even irony. However, an aesthetic ideal must inspire the audience to create and innovate.

In Uzbek ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic heritage, special attention is paid to the depiction of human beings, their beautiful and noble qualities, and their relationships of love and compassion toward both loved ones and others. Humanity, with its beautiful and noble spirituality and inner world, has always been a central focus for the subjects of folk art and culture. The idea of depicting the perfect human being and fostering a spiritually enriched generation was the primary goal of Uzbek ethnoculture.

As noted, "The idea of the perfect human being is both national and universal in nature. It embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection of humanity, constantly inspiring noble actions. This idea has not only guided individuals but also entire nations toward great progress, inspiring them to achieve unparalleled accomplishments in spirituality and enlightenment" (The Idea of National Independence: Fundamental Concepts and Principles, 2000. p. 56).

Perfection is an ideal that is difficult to attain. However, in the hearts and minds of the people, the aspiration toward this ideal has always been present. If we carefully examine the essence of oral folk art, epics, and even the lines, compositions, colors, and harmony in applied arts, we can see a clear striving for spiritual and psychological perfection.

For example, the works of Usta Fazil from Kokand, including intricately decorated trays, ewers, and teapots, are a testament to this aspiration for perfection. Usta Fazil, one of the most renowned artisans and metalworkers of his time, was born in Kokand in the 19th century. His works feature not only traditional patterns but also intricate designs born from his imagination. These designs combine geometry, floral elements, and depictions of nature. His metalwork is highly detailed, with every element executed flawlessly. The symmetry and harmony in his creations inspire both awe and tranquility. Usta Fazil's works also include depictions of fairies, winged animals, and mythical figures, adding a symbolic dimension to his creations.

The applied arts of Uzbek craftsmen, such as "giri" (geometric patterns), geometric designs, "kundal" (polychrome decorations), decorative entrance patterns, and ceiling ornaments, as well as the compositions of the Kokand and Tashkent decorative art schools that shaped national architecture, evoke pride not only for their uniqueness but also for their incredible complexity and perfection.

Conclusion

It is challenging to discern the inherent characteristics and features of ethnoculture without scientifically studying and observing the traditional aspects of ethno-aesthetic heritage. Ethno-aesthetic heritage is closely connected with various domains and topics, including cultural-economic types, socio-cultural life, communicative (diachronic and synchronic) relations, transcendental and theo-mythological concepts, rituals and public performances, traditional folk art and culture, significant processes within ethnoculture, and ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic ideals. The artistic-aesthetic values preserved in these areas, along with the transformation processes they have undergone, testify to the dynamic nature of ethnoculture.

In ethnoculture, traditionalism and modernity manifest not only according to the inherent laws of culture but also in response to constant influences, demands, and needs. The adaptation of inherent characteristics to permanent needs and demands results in transformations within ethnoculture. However, this transformation can alter certain forms, manifestations, and methods of artistic and aesthetic expression within ethnoculture.

Studying the aesthetic aspects of ethnoculture helps people understand their historical roots, national values, and cultural connections. Through the exploration of its aesthetic dimensions, individuals learn to appreciate uniqueness and beauty. The aesthetic aspects of ethnoculture are expressed in songs, dances, crafts, architecture, and traditional clothing. Researching and revitalizing these elements ensures the transmission of historical heritage to future generations. These aesthetic features instill a sense of pride and respect for one's culture, encouraging the protection and promotion of national heritage.

The aesthetic elements of ethnoculture also serve as a source of inspiration in the fields of art, design, and craftsmanship. Innovations derived from national aesthetics bring new spirit and meaning to contemporary art and design. Furthermore, the aesthetics of ethnoculture play a crucial role in fostering mutual understanding and respect among different nations and cultures. During intercultural dialogue, aesthetic aspects help individuals understand other cultures better.

In conclusion, studying the aesthetic aspects of ethnoculture not only preserves the historical and cultural wealth of a nation but also significantly contributes to the spiritual, social, and creative development of society. This work is essential for strengthening national identity and improving cultural interactions.

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